

HPLC and CE analysis of catechins, stilbens and quercetin in flowers and stems of *Polygonum cuspidatum*, *P. sachalinense* and *P. x bohemicum*

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Abstract : This study was designed to study the phenolic contents of above-ground parts of all three knotweed species, which have not been investigated yet. Phenolic compounds in methanolic extract of knotweed species (*Polygonum cuspidatum* Siebold and Zucc., *P. sachalinense* (F. Schmidt) and *P. x bohemicum* (Chrtek and Chrtková) Zika and Jacobson, Polygonaceae) were investigated using high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and capillary electrophoresis (CE). Dried samples of flowers and stems were used. We determined catechins, piceid and free quercetin and a large amount of total quercetin in the flowers, and epicatechin, chlorogenic acid, resveratrol, piceid and resveratrol derivative in the stems of all investigated species. Differences in contents of found compounds among species and between parts of plant bodies were ascertained ($P < 0.001$). The more content of total quercetin was determined in the flowers than in the stems. The results showed that the stems are rich with piceid and chlorogenic acid in *P. cuspidatum* (about 238 and 103 mg/kg of dry mass, respectively) and the flowers with quercetin-3- β -D-glucoside in *P. sachalinense* (about 5709 mg/kg of dry mass).

Keywords : Biological activity, CE, HPLC, knotweed, phenolic compounds, *Reynoutria*.

Introduction

The knotweed plant penetrated to Europe from East Asia at the beginning of the nineteenth century. It represents an invasive plant, which spreads along roads, waterways, dumps, abandoned and degraded fields¹. The knotweed occurs in gardens on the periphery of towns cultivated as an ornamental plant. When uncontrolled, it creates a high, compact growth which suppresses the other plant species and occupies always more and more space. Knotweed is a very persistent invasive plant², which suppresses the original plants and in this way it lessens the biological diversity everywhere it penetrates. Therefore knotweed has spread in Europe and other world regions³⁻⁵.

The knotweed genus belongs to the Polygonaceae family. There are three species of knotweeds in the area of the Czech Republic and Europe⁶.

(i) *Polygonum cuspidatum* Siebold and Zucc.; synonym : *Reynoutria japonica* (Houtt.) Ronse Decr., *Fallopia japonica* (Houtt.) Ronse Decr., *Pleuropterus cuspidatus* (Siebold and Zucc.) H. Gross in Lees, *Polygonum zuccarinii* Small, *Reynoutria hendryi* Nakai, *Tiniaria japonica* (Houtt.) Hedberg, English name : Japanese knotweed.

(ii) *Polygonum sachalinense* (F. Schmidt); synonym : *Reynoutria sachalinensis* (F. Schmidt) Nakai, *Fallopia sachalinensis* (F. Schmidt) Ronse Decr., *Pleuropterus sachalinensis* (F. Schmidt) H. Gross, *Tiniaria sachalinensis* (F. Schmidt) Janch, English name : Giant knotweed.

(iii) *Polygonum x bohemicum* (Chrtek and Chrtková) Zika and Jacobson (hybrid of *P. cuspidatum* and *P. sachalinense*); synonym : *Reynoutria x bohémica* Chrtek and Chrtková, *Reynoutria x vivax* Schmitz and Strank, English name : Bohemian knotweed.

The knotweed plants have high content of biologically

active substances, for example stilbens. Stilbens are substances with antioxidative, antimicrobial, anticarcinogenic and fungicide effects. Resveratrol also prevents cardiovascular diseases. The investigation is concentrated on the study of resveratrol, piceid and other stilbens in the roots of Japanese knotweed⁷⁻¹². Resveratrol was found also in many other plants but in low concentrations (e.g. in the plants *Cichorium* genus)¹³.

In the roots of Japanese knotweed were found several other biologically active substances with estrogenic activity, e.g. emodin and other derivatives of 9,10-anthraquinone^{9,10,14,15}. Glycosides of anthraquinones from Giant knotweed roots show allelopathic characteristics, inhibit lettuce seedling growth¹⁶. Extracts from autumn leaves and rhizomes of *P. cuspidatum*, *P. sachalinense* and *P. x bohemicum* strongly inhibit germination and growth white mustard^{17,18}. Pavela with colleagues¹⁹ demonstrated insecticide properties of extracts from leaves of *P. cuspidatum*, *P. sachalinense* and *P. x bohemicum*, the extracts inhibited growth *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae. The extracts from Giant knotweed contained substances with fungicide effects. They are used for plant protection²⁰⁻²³.

The pattern of phenolic compounds in the above-ground part of this three knotweeds was not described in detail. Our team found there some catechins, derivatives of caffeic acid, glycosides of quercetin in the leaves²⁴ and stilbens and catechins in the spring sprouts of *Polygonum*

cuspidatum, *P. sachalinense* and *P. x bohemicum*²⁵. Zhang with colleagues²⁶ isolated three anthraquinones and three derivatives of quercetin in the flower of *P. sachalinense*. Huang with colleagues²⁷ determined for example glycosides of quercetin and apigenin, emodin and its derivatives, rhein, gallic acid, piceid in mixture leaves and stems in *P. cuspidatum*. In this contribution we dealt with flowers and stems of all three species of knotweed, which are not investigated much.

Results

In the extracts from stems we detected epicatechin, chlorogenic acid, resveratrol and two of its glycosides (resveratrolside and piceid), trace amount quercetin-3-D-galactoside, free quercetin (Fig. 1). In the flowers we detected catechin, epicatechin, quercetin-3- β -D-glucoside, piceid, free quercetin (Fig. 2) and many of glycosides of quercetin (Fig. 3). As the standards of derivatives of quercetin (glycosides) are not easily accessed, we determined total quercetin after acid hydrolysis, as it was described in Methods. The stems contain several times smaller amounts of the total quercetin than flowers (Fig. 3). The content of total quercetin in flowers reaches the scale of about 11100–19500 mg/kg. Resveratrol, resveratrolside and chlorogenic acid were under the detection limit in the extracts from flowers.

Fig. 1. The means with standard errors of investigated compounds (mg/kg of dry mass) in the stems of *Polygonum* species.

Note

Fig. 2. The means with standard errors of investigated compounds (mg/kg of dry mass) in the flowers of *Polygonum* species.

Fig. 3. The contents of total quercetin (mg/kg of dry mass) in the flowers and stems of *Polygonum* species. The samples were prepared by mixing of the same amounts of dry mass from five plants of each species.

Significant differences were confirmed in many of detected compound contents (without resveratrol) among all three species of knotweed. Changes in the relative concentrations in stems and flowers of the knotweeds have been established ($P < 0.001$). We found the difference between plant parts (stem and flower) in the compound

contents, and among investigated species (interaction of species vs part of plant). Many fold higher contents of piceid, epicatechin, and chlorogenic acid were discovered in the stems of *P. cuspidatum*, than in the other knotweeds (Fig. 1). The contents of these substances were significantly different in all three species ($P < 0.001$). In

the flowers of *P. sachalinense* there was a significantly higher amount of quercetin-3- β -D-glucoside than that in the other species.

Discussion

The same biologically active compounds are present both in the roots and above-ground parts of knotweeds, but the amount of content is significantly different. There is also a difference among the species of knotweeds. Knotweeds are plants with extremely high concentrations of some biologically active substances, e.g. stilbens (rhizomes of *P. cuspidatum*) and total quercetin (above-ground part of knotweeds), they also contain a large amount of catechin and epicatechin. For example, rhizomes of *P. cuspidatum* contain a few grams of resveratrol per one kilogram of dry material⁷, but in rhizomes of *P. sachalinense* is the content of resveratrol 70 fold lower¹¹. Relatively high amounts of catechins and stilbens are in the spring sprouts of knotweeds species²⁵.

The dominant phenolic compound in methanolic extracts from flowers and leaves was aglycon quercetin, which belongs to the most wide-spread phenolic compounds in plant kingdom. Flowers contain 4 fold more total quercetin than leaves²⁴. The smallest amount of total quercetin was in leaves, flowers and stems of the hybrid of *R. x bohemica*. In the flowers of knotweed species there was much more total quercetin than in flowers of e.g. black elder⁸. Black elder (*Sambucus nigra* L.) is a popular healing herb in Central Europe, so flowers of knotweeds may be used as a medicinal herb, too.

Stilbens, namely piceid, were found in flowers and stems, but in comparison with roots, only in a minute content. We also identified stilbens in leaves. On the contrary to Vaher and Koel²⁹, we did not identify resveratrol in the methanolic extract from flowers. They found that some percentage of the total amount of resveratrol was found in flowers in the autumn, in the summer the content of resveratrol was very low. They extract flavonoids with supercritical fluid extraction that provides higher yield. The content of resveratrol and other stilbenes in roots of two varieties of *P. cuspidatum* is also influenced by geographical origin of the collected plant materials⁷. Fan with colleagues³⁰ found the phytochemical differences between extracts of roots and stems from *P. cuspidatum* and *P. sachalinense* collected in China and

Switzerland. They identified piceid, glucosides of quercetin and the number of glucosides of coumaric acid in stems of the species. We determined piceid in the stem extracts, especially in *P. cuspidatum*, but we also found small amounts of other stilbens and epicatechin (Fig. 1). We found the compounds with spectrum similar to spectrum of coumaric acid, but we did not determine them. It seems that the contents of phenolic compounds may be influenced by geographical origin.

Catechins, stilbens, derivatives of quercetin are known for their antioxidative and allelopathic characteristics³¹⁻³³. Thus we assume that the viability of knotweeds and their invasive properties are probably connected with the high concentration of biologically active phenolic compounds. Antimicrobial and fungicidal effect of these compounds may be the reason why dead masses of knotweed decay slowly and incompletely.

Experimental

Plant material : The stems from three species of knotweed (*P. cuspidatum*, *P. sachalinense* and *P. x bohemicum*) were collected in May flowers in September 2002 in the Český Krumlov district (Czech Republic). Plant material was collected and identified by Božena Šerá (co-author). Voucher specimens are kept in the herbarium of the Southern Bohemian Museum in České Budějovice. We took five specimens for each sample.

Extract preparation : The stems and flowers were dried at laboratory temperature and then pulverized. Each sample of 0.25 g was extracted 30 min with 3 ml 60% methanol. After centrifugation the sediment was two times eluted with 1 ml 60% methanol. The supernatants from the same sample were joined. We prepared five extracts from flowers and five extracts from stems of each knotweed; each sample was prepared separately.

Extract analysis : The samples were analysed using HPLC (Hewlett Packard 1050) with a DAD detector (Hewlett Packard 1040A) on Phenomenex Luna C18 column (2 × 150 mm, 3 μ m), in water-acetonitrile gradient with the addition of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) at 25 °C. Injected volume was 5 μ l. Chromatographic mobile phase A : 5% acetonitrile with 0.1% *o*-phosphoric acid, mobile phase B : 80% acetonitrile with 0.1% *o*-phosphoric acid. The separation of phenolic compounds was carried out using gradient : 0 to 53% of solvent B in 55 min with the

flow rate of 0.25 ml min⁻¹. Stilbens (resveratrol and its derivatives) were detected at 315 nm and other phenolic compounds at 220 nm. We calculated resveratrolside by calibrating curve of resveratrol, others compounds were calculated by use of calibrating curves of their standards. Chromatographic data of determined phenolic compounds are in Table 1. On the basis of literature data we suppose that derivative of resveratrol with RT 19.9 min is resveratrolside.

Table 1: Chromatographic data of determined phenolic compound

Phenolic compound	RT (min)	Acetonitrile (%)
Catechin	13.49	14.75
Chlorogenic acid	13.51	14.77
Epicatechin	17.43	17.60
Resveratrolside	19.94	19.41
Piceid	23.87	22.25
Quercetin-3-D-galactoside	25.09	23.13
Quercetin-3-D-glucoside	25.50	23.43
Resveratrol	33.01	28.86
Quercetin	38.47	32.81

The standards of piceid were obtained from Chromadex, quercetin-3-β-D-glucoside and quercetin-3-D-galactoside from Fluka; resveratrol, catechins, chlorogenic acid and quercetin were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

For determination of total quercetin (five specimen of each species were mixed in the same proportion and extracted with 50% methanol) the extracts were hydrolyzed in 50% methanol with 6 M hydrochloric acid (2 h, 90 °C) and then purified on a SPE column (C₁₈). After purification, the samples were analyzed using CE (Spectra-Phoresis 2000) with UV detector, and 10 mM borate buffer (pH 9.2) with addition of SDS (20 mM) and methanol (15%). Quercetin was detected at 270 nm³⁴.

Statistics of analysis : To find out the difference in the content of the investigated substances differs in individual species and plant body parts, we used hierarchical (nested) design ANOVA test in the programme STATISTICA³⁵. Independent variables were the plant species (three *Polygonum* species), body parts (stem, flower), individual plant (5 individuals). The dependent variable is the total content of studied compound. In the split-plot design, a factor species was regarded as the main factor, the whole

plot factor was a part of plant body, and the within-plot factor was an individual plant. The factor of individual plant was nested in the factor species and was calculated as a random effect³⁶. Such design was used separately for the content of each detected compound.

Conclusion :

The studies of knotweed species differ from each other not only in appearance but also in the content of various phenolic compounds. All the parts of plant body contain the set of approximately the same compounds, but they differ in the amounts of these substances. The flowers are rich in quercetin derivatives, the roots in stilbenes (especially *P. cuspidatum*).

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